

THE MORAL OF ADAPTIVE PHYSICAL EDUCATION IN YOUNG CHILDREN

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Annotation.

This article covers the role and relevance of adaptive physical education in the process of adapting children with disabilities to social life. The corrective and developmental direction of pedagogical influences is the basis of individual methods of adaptive physical culture.

Keywords.

adaptive physical culture, mental and emotional ability, wellness classes, correction, children, action games

Introduction. The direction of Correction and development is characteristic of all educational work and covers all categories of children with developmental disabilities. The corrective and developmental direction of adaptive physical culture has a wide range of solutions to pedagogical problems.

The corrective and developmental direction of adaptive physical culture has a wide range of solutions to pedagogical problems. They can be conditionally combined into the following groups:

1. correction of basic movements in walking, running, swimming, throwing, jumping, skiing, exercising with objects, etc.;
2. correction and development of coordination skills;
3. correction and development of physical fitness,
4. correction and Prevention of somatic diseases;
5. prevention, correction and development of mental and emotional abilities;
6. development of cognitive activity;
7. formation of the personality of the child.

Forms of Organization of physical culture adapted with children . The adaptive physical culture structure includes adaptive physical education, adaptive motion rest, adaptive sports, and physical rehabilitation. Each type has its own purpose: adaptive physical education is designed to form the basic foundations of

physical education; adapted motorized rest - for healthy rest, outdoor play, games, communication; adaptive sports-for the improvement and implementation of physical, mental, emotional and volitional abilities; physical rehabilitation-to treat, restore and compensate for lost abilities. Each of them has its own functions, tasks, content, level of emotional and mental stress, methods and forms of organization. At the same time, they are closely related and complement each other. The basic form of classes organized in all types of adaptive physical culture is a form of lesson that justifies itself historically and empirically.

Depending on the goals, objectives, content of the program, classes are conditionally distinguished:

- for training - to form special knowledge, to teach various motor skills;
- for classes in the direction of Correction and development - for the development and correction of physical qualities and coordination abilities. correction of emotional systems and mental functions using exercise;
- for wellness classes – to straighten the torso, flat feet, prevent somatic diseases, disorders of the emotional system, strengthen the cardiovascular and respiratory systems;
- for therapeutic classes - for the treatment, restoration and compensation of lost or impaired functions in chronic diseases, injuries, etc. (for example, daily exercise therapy classes in special school-Centers for children with cerebral palsy);
- for sports training - improving physical, technical, tactical, mental, volitional, theoretical training in the chosen sport;
- for recreational classes-for organized leisure, leisure, gaming activities.

Extracurricular forms are not regulated by Time, place of classes, number of participants, their age.

In Special (Correctional) educational institutions, Adapted Physical Education is carried out in the following forms:

- * physical culture classes;
- rhythm lessons (in elementary grades;
- physical education training in general education classes (to eliminate and prevent mental fatigue).

The following chapters reveal the characteristics of the method of adaptive physical culture of children from different nosological groups. Methods and organization of outdoor games with Blind Children. General requirements for the game. The game should correspond to the age of the children, their physical development and the skills they have. When choosing equipment for blind children, the head of the game should try to ensure that it is bright and colorful,

take into account the contrast of objects, use colors (green, red, orange, yellow) that best affect visual perception. When using the ball, you can follow the following recommendations.

1. For the game, the ball must be taken in a very rounded manner, providing an angle of descent equal to the angle of the mirror so that it falls directly into the player's hands.

2. The ball should be slightly heavier than volleyball. The heavy ball is well felt by the blind, and that they master the game with it rather than a light ball is possible. The choice of color 'p' depends on the light. In case of insufficient light, it is necessary to use a light-colored ball, in bright light-dark. It is advisable to use a sound ball that allows a child with a visual impairment not only to play freely with him, throw him clearly, catch him easily, but also find him on his own.
3. The equipment used must be safe. It is necessary to ensure the safety of the playground, determine its size, build limiting signs: sand-covered grooves slightly above the level of the entire playground; gravel strip, grass cover; paved road, rubber mats and other embossed (tactile) marks, cord; stretched along the perimeter of the site. There should be no tails, holes, bushes, fences on the site - its surface should be the same. The guide lines can be marked with colored pencils or a colored cloth line. Players must first familiarize themselves with the size of the playground and all possible characters (sight, hearing, sense of smell, etc.), allowing them to walk around, Run, see everything and equipment used in the game. The leader uses a signal to guide players, give the correct direction, and warn of danger. A child with a visual impairment feels the whole game mainly through a hearing analyzer, which can experience excessive tension of the auditory organs, nervous system, so it is necessary to regulate physical activity during the game. Correction games are given as illustrations. Open games for blind children are played by an odd number of players aimed at correcting posture (for students in grades 1-4), such as five rings placed in a circle. Children walk in the outer circle and perform various standing exercises. In the words of the leader: "stop, children, don't yawn! Choose a pair quickly! players run into rings, pair up and stand with their backs on each other, taking a predetermined correct position. The player who turns out to be superfluous enters the circle and, along with the leader, marks the players in the wrong position. A player who fails to perform the exercise correctly receives a penalty point, while the player who remains without a pair receives two penalties. The person with the fewest penalties is the winner. Exercises aimed at forming the correct posture:

1. walking on the toes, hands behind the head, elbows to the side, joining the shoulder blades;
2. semi-elongated (straight back) walk, focusing on the sound signals located at different ends of the Hall;
3. walking with backward circular movements of the hands (keeping the head straight, distance), paying attention to the Step sound of the person in front;
4. easy running while maintaining the correct posture.

Children's reception in a standing position on the ring: hands to the side, palms to the front; put your hands on the shoulder with your palms forward, join the shoulder blades ("duck"). "Rabbits". Teams line up in columns one after the other in front of the starting line. In front of the guides are sandbags measuring 10 x 20 cm. At a distance of 4 m from the Start line, rotating flags (sound signal) are installed. The host says, "jumping-jumping, jumping-jumping, rabbits are jumping, white side. Through the forest, up to the Bush separated by snow. With the last word, the instructions on the Poles take the bag and put it on the head, take the position of the hand on the belt, the elbows move back, the back is flat, and the jumps (running) move towards the flags. Turning their flag, they take the bags and run to their teams, giving a voice signal to their comrades. They give the bag to the next player and stand at the end of the column themselves. If the bag has fallen, it must be lifted and placed on the head and continue jumping. The game continues until the guides again stand in front of their superiors. They raise their arms up. The team that finishes the relay first wins. "Cosmonauts". In the center of the hall, a circle with a diameter of 2-2.5 M is marked with chalk, around which rings (colored) are fixed at a distance of 2 m. A large circle is Earth, and rings are rockets. Each team has only two places. A few people are playing more than the seats on the Rockets. The children stand one by one outside the circle. According to the order of the leader, they walk and perform movements that shape the torso, while reading the recitative: "fast Rockets await us to walk on the planet; whichever we want, we fly to such a place. But there is one secret in the game: there is no place for delays! With The Last Word, players scatter in different directions and occupy any rocket in pairs. Standing in a ring facing the ground, the children raise it, pull the shoulder blades and shout "come out!" command. with side steps, they move in a circle, then with the command "landing" everyone stops. As the astronauts fly, the late ones stand in the center of a large circle and wave their hands. The game is repeated several times. At the end of the game, children who have flown more are marked.

In conclusion, the choice of action games in which children with physical disabilities are organized outdoors is aimed at making them energize their body

through physical activity and, through it, adapt to social life . The adaptive physical culture structure includes adaptive physical education, adaptive motion rest, adaptive sports, and physical rehabilitation. Each type has its own purpose: adaptive physical education is designed to form the basic foundations of physical education; adapted motorized recreation - for healthy recreation, outdoor play, games, communication; adaptive sports - for the improvement and implementation of physical, mental, emotional and volitional abilities; physical rehabilitation-is used to treat, restore and compensate for lost abilities.

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